

(40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ether in different solvent ratios gave different products (Table 1).

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steroidal diols (1-3)² with lead(IV) acetate in dry benzene and a catalytic amount of iodine.

Ir spectra of the 6β,19-oxido-5-hydroxy-5α-cholestanes (4-6) exhibited characteristic bands at 3 460-3 430 cm⁻¹ (OH), 2 950-2 940s (CH) and 1 240-1 225 cm⁻¹ (epoxide linkage). The ¹H nmr spectra revealed C-6 proton at δ 5.3-5.2, C-3 proton at δ 4.7-3.4 and 19 C-H_a protons at δ 4.2-4.1. The mass spectral fragmentations (Scheme 1) of 4-6 were as anticipated³, thus supporting the assigned structures of the compounds.

Scheme 1

Synthesis of 6β,19-Oxido-steroids

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THERE a number of reports¹ on the synthesis of 6β,19-oxidosteroids from steroidal bromohydrins and epoxides. Here, we report the synthesis of 3β-substituted-6β,19-oxido-5-hydroxy-5α-cholestane derivatives (4-6) by the reaction of

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were determined on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A 60 instrument (60 Hz) with Me₄Si as the internal standard and mass spectra on a JeOL-D 300 spectrometer at 70 eV. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4-6*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	δ^{**}
4	135	41	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O ₂ Cl	3 430 (OH), 2 950 (CH), 1 240 (epoxide linkage), 730 (C-Cl)	5.3 (1H, br s, C6-αH), 4.1 (2H, br s, C19-H _a), 3.5 (1H, mc, W _{1/2} 16 Hz, C3-αH) 2.1 (1H, s, C5-αOH)
5	101	40	C ₂₉ H ₄₆ O ₄	3 440 (OH), 2 940 (CH), 1 725, 1 240 (CH ₃ COO), 1 225 (epoxide linkage)	5.2 (1H, br s, C6-αH), 4.2 (2H, br s, C19-H _a), 4.7 (1H, mc, W _{1/2} 18 Hz, C3-αH), 2.2 (1H, s, C5-αOH), 2.0 (3H, s, CH ₃ COO)
6	Oil	40	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O ₂	3 460-3 400 (OH), 2 950 (CH), 1 235 (epoxide linkage)	5.3 (1H, br s, C6-αH), 4.2 (2H, br s, C19-H _a), 3.4 (1H, mc, W _{1/2} 18 Hz, C3-αH), 2.1 (1H, s, C5-αOH)

*All compounds showed satisfactory C and H analyses.

**Angular and side-chain methyl protons appeared at δ 0.95-0.69.

General procedure: Lead(IV) acetate (11.3 mmol) was added in portions in the presence of catalyst amount of iodine (1 g) to the steroidal diol (1.78 mmol) dissolved in dry benzene (90 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h and the progress of reaction was monitored by tlc. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was taken in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent gave a solid which was recrystallised from methanol to yield the products (Table 1).

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Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of some Novel *N*-[2-(Phenoxy/bromo/nitro/substituted-phenoxy)acetyl/propionyl]carbazole

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PHENOXYACETIC acid, phenoxypropionic acid, and carbazole and its various derivatives possess a wide spectrum of biological activities¹. These results prompted us to undertake the synthesis of some new *N*-[2-phenoxy/bromo/nitro/substituted-phenoxy)acetyl/propionyl]carbazole (1) and to screen their anti-inflammatory and anticonvulsant properties.

The carbazole derivatives of the compounds have been synthesised by reacting substituted

phenoxy derivatives with sodium salt of chloroacetic/propionic acids in good yields. The structures of all the compounds have been established on the basis of spectral data and elemental analysis (Table 1)

1

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds were checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. Various phenoxy acetic acid, propionic acid their bromo, nitro substituted derivatives were synthesised by condensing the sodium salt of the appropriate phenol with $\text{ClCH}_2\text{COONa}$ and $\text{ClCH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{COONa}$. To a solution of aryloxy acid (0.04 mol in 50 ml of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6/\text{EtOAc}$) was added thionyl chloride (0.05 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The acid chloride was added dropwise to an ice-cold solution of carbazole (0.036 mol in 25 ml EtOAc) and 2*N* NaOH solution (5 ml) with constant stirring. The separated amide was filtered, washed and purified over a column of silica gel. Ir spectra displayed principal absorptions at 2900–2930 (CH_3), 1600–1330 (aromatic NO_2), 1228–1240 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{N}$), 1110–1250 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$) and 690–720 cm^{-1} (aromatic substitution pattern).

Biological evaluation: Anti-inflammatory activity of the compounds (1a–l) were tested in albino rats weighing 100–120 g (fated overnight) by the reported method². The percentage inhibition of inflammation after 3 h was calculated³. The results suggested that compounds 1b, c, j, k, l displayed promising activity which is nearly equal to that of the standard drug ibuprofen.

The anticonvulsant activity of all the compounds was recorded following the reported method⁴. The results suggested that the compounds 1b, c, j, k, l exhibited greater anticonvulsant activity using pentylenetetrazole.

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